

DAMAGE REPRESENTATION AND DAMAGE EVOLUTION FOR TRANSVERSE CRACKING OF LINEAR VISCOELASTIC UD COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to build a damage model for linear viscoelastic UD (unidirectional) composites undergoing transverse matrix cracking. The damage representation for the corresponding elastic UD composites with an array of dispersed matrix cracks was derived using continuum damage mechanics (CDM) based on S. Li's work. The elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle (CP) was used to obtain the damage representation for corresponding linear viscoelastic UD composites in the Laplace domain. The damage representation for linear viscoelastic UD composites in the time domain was obtained by taking the inverse Laplace transformation. A damage evolution law was constructed by using the Weibull distribution of defects which can be developed into cracks by strain. The time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) approach is interpreted by this model. The application of this damage model is described and the predictions are compared with experimental data.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behaviour of polymer resins exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behaviour. In the aviation industry where composites are widely used, it is necessary to estimate the properties of the composites. Unlike the metals they replace, the timescales cannot be validly ignore when considering the loading regimes to which they are subjected as the viscoelastic behaviour of the composites we mentioned. In particular, airframes have long lifetimes (up to 50 years) during which they will be subjected to complex loading cycles involving frequency components as low as around 10^{-5} Hz (one cycle per day) as well as much higher frequency components. Direct replication of the load cases within fatigue tests is clearly not feasible due to the timescales involved; and also high-frequency fatigue tests (such as those used with metal) cannot be directly used as they take no account of the creep taking place within each cycle. We want to take advantage of viscoelastic behaviour of UD composites to accelerate fatigue and long-term creep tests. This paper is a step towards this ultimate objective.

By contrast with the time-independent linear elastic case, the constitutive equations for this kind of viscoelastic material is written in an integral form using the well-known Boltzman superposition principle. In order to describe the properties of the viscoelastic material, it is necessary to build both a damage representation and a law describing damage evolution during deformation.

1.1 Damage representation

Talreja [1] built a damage representation for composites based on continuum damage mechanics. In this model, damage was described by a set of internal vector field variables. The damage state was derived from the constitutive equation for the isothermal, small-deformation behaviour of composites.

For small damage, the residual elastic properties can be derived and related to the initial elastic properties. This model is helpful in assessing the properties of composites with small damage. However, the damage material constants still need to be determined precisely. Based on Talreja's work, Li [2] determined damage related constants for a transversely isotropic UD composite using ideal experiments. In his work, the damage caused by matrix cracks (with cracks surfaces perpendicular to the axis 2 is described by a reduction in stiffness. He also found there was an interaction between degradations of E_2 and G_{12} . However, this work related only to elastic UD composites and requires extension to cover the viscoelastic case. In order to achieve this using the thermodynamics of irreversible processes, Schapery [3, 4] developed modified CP based on the concepts of pseudo stress and pseudo strain. The concepts of pseudo strain energy density and pseudo complementary energy density were then introduced. Damage can be represented as internal state variables. The pseudo energy representation in terms of pseudo stresses or strains and damage is analogous to the strain energy of elasticity theories. However, these models are limited to materials in which all the properties can be represented by a single function of time, whereas for anisotropic materials, the time dependence in different directions is expected to involve different functions of time. Kumar [5, 6] built a damage representation for linear viscoelastic cross-ply laminate composite based on new functions for pseudo strain energy and pseudo complementary strain energy in the Laplace domain, which are extended from the elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle. Here the pseudo strain energy is a function of Laplace transformed strains and the pseudo complementary energy is a function of Laplace transformed stresses. These pseudo energies are different from the pseudo energies defined by Schapery [3] since they are based on different pseudo strain or pseudo stress. Kumar's model was focused on the cross-ply laminates with transverse matrix cracks in which damage is represented through internal variables taking the form of second rank tensors.

1.2 Damage evolution law

On its own, damage representation applies to a fixed level of damage and can be used to predict residual properties. However, this is just one state during the whole process of deformation, and in order to describe the behaviour of the material during the whole process of deformation, damage evolution should be incorporated into the damage representation. Damage evolution laws originated from the interpolation of experimental stress-strain curves, where empirical functions were devised to modify the linear elastic stress-strain responses into nonlinear ones for including the damage effect. However, this type of damage evolution law is normally only applicable to limited loading cases, because the damage evolution processes are essentially prescribed by independent functions, fitting to the experimental stress-strain curves obtained under specific loading cases involving damage.

In terms of derivation of damage evolution laws, two major approaches have been identified: one follows the concept of a damage surface which is similar to the concept of a yield surface in plasticity, the other is based on the derivation of damage driving force which is a concept analogous to energy release rate in fracture mechanics [7, 8]. Damage surface expressions are often derived from damage initiation criteria so that as soon as damage is initiated, the damage surface will be updated continuously during the subsequent damage evolution process. An incremental damage evolution law based on a damage surface can then be devised in a similar way to that in the incremental theory of plasticity. Li [9] developed a CDM model for characterizing transverse matrix cracks in laminates, by employing the concept of damage surface in order to formulate a damage evolution law. Damage driving force expressions are normally derived from energy functions of damaged materials. In the CDM model proposed by Ladeveze [10], strain energy density function of damaged UD composite was used to derive the damage driving force. By contrast, a specific Helmholtz free energy function was chosen by Talreja [1] to derive the damage driving force. Yu [11] built a damage evolution law based on the concept of damage driving force for modelling the evolution of matrix damage in UD composites. The damage evolution has the advantage of describing the damage evolution process in terms of total damage driving force which is naturally partitioned into three components directly associated with the corresponding stress components. This model is achieved through rigorous theoretical derivation and can be used for damage evolution of different types of the stresses. However the damage evolution laws

described above are all built based on elastic theory. We need to build damage evolution law for viscoelastic materials based on the viscoelastic theory.

This project aims to build both the damage representation and damage evolution for UD composites with specific cracks in a linear viscoelastic UD composites. The TTSP approach will be interpreted by this model. Some prediction will be verified by the experimental data.

2. CORRESPONDENCE PRINCIPLE

For elastic materials, the constitutive equation is a linear relationship between stress and strain and the generalized Hooke's law relating stresses to strains can be written in contracted notation [12] as

$$\sigma_i = C_{ij}\epsilon_j \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (2-1)$$

where σ_i are the stress components, C_{ij} is the stiffness matrix, and ϵ_j are the strain components. For a linear viscoelastic and non-aging material, the constitutive equations can be written in an integral form using the well-known Boltzman superposition principle as [6]

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(t)\epsilon_{kl}^0 + \int_0^t C_{ijkl}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (2-2)$$

or, inversely

$$\epsilon_{ij} = S_{ijkl}(t)\sigma_{kl}^0 + \int_0^t S_{ijkl}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial \sigma_{kl}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (2-3)$$

Here $C_{ijkl}(t)$ and $S_{ijkl}(t)$ are the relaxation modulus tensor and creep compliance tensor, respectively. Taking the Laplace transform of both sides of (2-2) and (2-3) and applying the convolution theorem, we obtain

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \bar{C}_{ijkl}\epsilon_{kl}^0 + \bar{C}_{ijkl} \cdot \left(\overline{\frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(\tau)}{\partial \tau}} \right) = \tilde{C}_{ijkl}\bar{\epsilon}_{kl} \quad (2-4)$$

and

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \bar{S}_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl}^0 + \bar{S}_{ijkl} \cdot \left(\overline{\frac{\partial \sigma_{kl}(\tau)}{\partial \tau}} \right) = \tilde{S}_{ijkl}\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \quad (2-5)$$

where $\epsilon_{kl}^0 = \epsilon_{kl}(0)$, $\sigma_{kl}^0 = \sigma_{kl}(0)$, the Laplace transform $\bar{f}(s)$ of a function $f(t)$ is defined as

$$\bar{f}(s) \equiv \mathcal{L}\{f(t)\} \equiv \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt \quad (2-6)$$

\tilde{C}_{ijkl} is the Carson transform of $C_{ijkl}(t)$ defined as $\tilde{C}_{ijkl} \equiv s\bar{C}_{ijkl}$ and \tilde{S}_{ijkl} is the Carson transform of $S_{ijkl}(t)$ defined as $\tilde{S}_{ijkl} \equiv s\bar{S}_{ijkl}$.

After taking the Laplace transformation, the integral constitutive equations transform to purely algebraic equations in the Laplace domain. (2-4) and (2-5) are analogous to the linear elastic constitutive equations except that they now relate to Laplace transformed stresses and strains. The constitutive equation of a linear viscoelastic material is time dependent. Since the Laplace transformation affects time but not spatial parameters, the corresponding viscoelastic operators obey analogous relations in the Laplace domain as the relations of the elastic operators in time domain [13]. If the solution for an elastic problem is obtained, then the solution for the corresponding viscoelastic problem can also be obtained by replacing all the material properties appeared in the elastic solution by their Carson transforms. The solution is thus obtained in the Laplace domain and needs to be inverted to obtain the time domain solution. This is the well-known correspondence principle of linear viscoelasticity theory [14], and it will enable the damage representation of elastic materials to be extended to the viscoelastic case.

3. DAMAGE REPRESENTATION

3.1 Damage representation of the elastic UD composite with matrix cracks

Based on continuum damage mechanics (CDM), Li [2] obtained an expression for the stiffness

modulus of UD composites with matrix cracks (the crack surface perpendicular to axis 2). There are three assumptions in his work, which are commonly employed explicitly or implicitly in damage theories.

- (1) The virgin material is homogeneous so that the heterogeneity between reinforcing fibres and the matrix can be neglected;
- (2) The virgin material is transversely isotropic. The damage to it takes a form of a single array of cracks, small in size but large in number, with a common orientation such that the damaged material demonstrates homogeneous orthotropic behaviour;
- (3) The matrix cracks concerned are all mathematical cracks having completely flat and closed crack surfaces under an unloaded condition and the material around the cracks is free from any initial stresses.

The compliance matrix of a UD composite can be expressed as

$$[S^0] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1^0 & & & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}^0/E_1^0 & 1/E_2^0 & & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}^0/E_1^0 & -\nu_{23}^0/E_2^0 & 1/E_2^0 & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23}^0 & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12}^0 & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12}^0 & \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Symm.} \quad (3-1)$$

Where $G_{23}^0 = \frac{E_2^0}{2(1+\nu_{23}^0)}$.

For any particular damage mode, matrix cracks have a common orientation with crack surfaces parallel to the fibre direction (axis 1). The damage is described by the stiffness reduction in direction 2. Then

$$E_2 = E_2^0(1 - D) \quad (3-2)$$

and the compliance with the damage in the form of matrix cracks perpendicular to direction 2 is

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1^0 & & & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}^0/E_1^0 & 1/[E_2^0(1 - D)] & & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}^0/E_1^0 & -\nu_{23}^0/E_2^0 & 1/E_2^0 & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\left[G_{23}^0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \nu_{23}^0)} D\right)\right] & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12}^0 & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/[G_{12}^0(1 - kD)] & \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Symm.} \quad (3-3)$$

The UD composites become orthotropic after undergoing damage and their properties can be derived from engineering constants of undamaged UD composites and damage variable as

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_1^0 & E_2 &= E_2^0(1 - D) & E_3 &= E_3^0 (= E_2^0) \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_{12}^0 & \nu_{13} &= \nu_{13}^0 (= \nu_{12}^0) & \nu_{32} &= \nu_{32}^0 (= \nu_{23}^0) \\ G_{13} &= G_{13}^0 (= G_{12}^0) & G_{23} &= G_{23}^0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \nu_{23}^0)} D\right) & G_{12} &= G_{12}^0 (1 - kD) \end{aligned} \quad (3-4)$$

3.2 Damage representation of a viscoelastic UD composite

The damage representation of an elastic UD composite can be extended to the viscoelastic case by replacing the engineering constants by the Carson transformation of the corresponding creep compliance.

$$[\tilde{S}] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\tilde{E}_1^0 & & & & & & \\ -\tilde{\nu}_{12}^0/\tilde{E}_1^0 & 1/[\tilde{E}_2^0(1 - \tilde{D})] & & & & & \\ -\tilde{\nu}_{12}^0/\tilde{E}_1^0 & -\tilde{\nu}_{23}^0/\tilde{E}_2^0 & 1/\tilde{E}_2^0 & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\left[\tilde{G}_{23}^0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \tilde{\nu}_{23}^0)} \tilde{D}\right)\right] & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\tilde{G}_{12}^0 & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/[\tilde{G}_{12}^0(1 - k\tilde{D})] & \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Symm.} \quad (3-5)$$

where $\hat{D} = 1 - \tilde{E}_2/\tilde{E}_2^0$.

It is noted that $[\tilde{S}]$ is the creep compliance in the Laplace domain. Then creep compliance, the damage representation in the time domain can be obtained by taking the inverse Laplace transformation of $[\tilde{S}]$.

The Carson's transformed conventional engineering constants such as \tilde{E}_1^0 , \tilde{E}_2^0 , $\tilde{\nu}_{12}^0$, $\tilde{\nu}_{23}^0$ and \tilde{G}_{12}^0 can be obtained from stress relaxation tests. Then the damage representation of viscoelastic UD composites with matrix cracks can be obtained in the Laplace domain by combining the damage variable \hat{D} which is controlled by a damage evolution law and k can be measured from experiments.

4. DAMAGE EVOLUTION LAW

The damage representation of transverse linear viscoelastic UD composites can be obtained from the extension of damage representation of elastic case by taking advantage of correspondence principle. Unfortunately, the CP only can be used in cases where essential and natural boundaries are independent of time such as fixed cracks [15]. We need to build a damage evolution law based on viscoelastic theory. The damage evolution law does not need to be as complicated as we mentioned since we just need it useful enough. We can start to build damage evolution law in one dimension.

4.1 The Wiechert model

The most validated mathematical model to describe viscoelasticity in 1 dimensional is the Wiechert model (Figure 1). In this model, viscoelasticity is described by a series of springs (elasticity) and dashpots (viscosity) connected in parallel.

Figure 1: The Wiechert model.

The relaxation modulus for this model is

$$E_{rel}(t) = k_e + \sum_j k_j \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_j}\right) \quad (4-1)$$

Where k_e is the Young's modulus of the main spring, k_j is the Young's modulus of spring connected with a dashpot, τ_j is the relaxation time and

$$\tau_j = \frac{\eta_j}{k_j} \quad (4-2)$$

where η_j is the viscosity of the dashpot.

In the theory of CDM, the effects of damage are likely to be reflected in the reduction of stiffness modulus [16, 17], as shown in equation (3-2).relating to matrix cracking in direction 2. For viscoelastic materials, it will be assumed that the damage affects each part of the Wiechert model equally.

Then the relaxation modulus with damage can be defined as

$$E_D(t) = (1 - D) \left[k_e + \sum_j k_j \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_j}\right) \right] \quad (4-3)$$

Where $E_D(t)$ can be $E_2(t)$ (transverse modulus) in the present representation of damage in three dimensions.

4.2 Damage evolution law for matrix or transverse direction of the UD composites

As the matrix cracks in direction 2 can be described by the CDM, then we can build a damage evolution law for it to construct a complete damage model. It has been found that UD composites failed at the same strain in the transverse tensile test and the transverse bending test [18]. The damage evolution law is described by a Weibull distribution of the defects in the matrix or transverse UD composites, which can be developed into damage (crack) by strain.

It will be supposed that there is a representative volume element (RVE) in a UD composite containing a large number of different size/level defects in this RVE. These defects can be developed into damage (cracks) by the corresponding strain during deformation. Then the sizes/levels of the defects can be described by the corresponding strain which can develop the defects into damage. Then the probability density of these defects can be described by the Weibull distribution which is function of strain.

$$d(\epsilon; \lambda, h) = \begin{cases} \frac{h}{\lambda} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\lambda}\right)^{h-1} e^{-\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\lambda}\right)^h} & \sigma \geq 0 \\ 0 & \sigma < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4-4)$$

Where h and λ are constants. Then

$$D = \int_0^\epsilon d \, dx = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\lambda}\right)^h} \quad (4-5)$$

The constitutive equation of the viscoelastic material is presented by (2-2) or (2-3) and the relaxation modulus with damage is expressed as (4-3) due to the assumption that damage occurs in every part of the Wiechert model. Then the constitutive equation of the damaged viscoelastic material is

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(t) &= E_D(t) \epsilon_0 + \int_0^t E_D(t-\tau) \frac{\partial \epsilon(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ &= e^{-\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\lambda}\right)^h} \left[k_e + \sum_j k_j \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_j}\right) \right] \epsilon_0 \\ &\quad + e^{-\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\lambda}\right)^h} \int_0^t \left[k_e + \sum_j k_j \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\tau_j}\right) \right] \frac{\partial \epsilon(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (4-6)$$

Where $\epsilon = \int_0^t \frac{\partial \epsilon(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau$ and $\epsilon = \epsilon_0$ when $t = 0$. Then (4-6) is the damage evolution of the viscoelastic material. It is noted that the relaxation modulus reduction $(1 - D)$ is taken outside the convolution no matter whether damage variable D is a function of time t . The damage effect is independent of the Boltzman superposition principle in describing the viscoelastic materials during deformation. This means the damage variable D is independent of the time effect of the viscoelasticity in the damage representation represented by (3-5). The damage variable \hat{D} can therefore be replaced by damage variable D . This makes the damage model complete.

A constant strain rate test can be taken as an example. If the static test is controlled by a constant strain rate a , then (4-6) will transform into

$$\sigma(t) = a e^{-\left(\frac{at}{\lambda}\right)^h} \left\{ k_e t + \sum_j \left[k_j \tau_j - k_j \tau_j \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_j}\right) \right] \right\} \quad (4-7)$$

As shown in Kumar[6] and Koyanagi's [19] paper, there is no elastic part of the Wiechert model in describing the properties of the neat resin or transverse properties of the UD composites. Then (4-7)

can be further simplified as

$$\sigma(t) = ae^{-\left(\frac{at}{\lambda}\right)^h} \cdot \sum_j \left[k_j \tau_j - k_j \tau_j \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_j}\right) \right] \quad (4-8)$$

The constant strain rate strength (maximum stress) is then determined by (4-8) and the testing time to reach the maximum stress is determined by

$$\frac{d\sigma(t)}{dt} = 0 \quad (4-9)$$

5. INTERPRETATION OF THE TIME-TEMPERATURE SUPERPOSITION PRINCIPLE (TTSP)

The mechanical behaviour of viscoelastic composites can be attributed to the rearrangement of long chain molecules in polymers [20], which exhibit time and temperature dependence which exacerbates the difficulty in describing this kind of material since the constitutive equation is an integral form. However, this time and temperature dependence also presents the opportunity to accelerate fatigue and long-term creep tests. The time-temperature superposition principle can be used to determine temperature-dependent mechanical properties of linear viscoelastic materials from known properties at a reference temperature. These properties increase with loading rate but decrease when the temperature is increased [21]. Fortunately, curves of these properties as functions of time do not change shape as the temperature is changed but appear only to shift left or right when plotted on a logarithmic time axis. This implies that a master curve at a given temperature can be used as the reference to predict curves at various temperatures by applying a shift operation. The time-temperature superposition principle of linear viscoelasticity is based on the above observation [14]. Miyano and Nakada performed much work on accelerating fatigue test and predicting fatigue life by using TTSP [22-25]. But the simple application of a time-temperature shift factor and the reduced time in the axial direction of the UD composite make this approach arbitrary and questionable. The present work aims to interpret the TTSP approach by making use of the viscoelastic damage model presented here.

τ_j can be replaced with η_j and k_j in (4-1), so that

$$E_{rel}(t) = k_e + \sum_j k_j \exp\left(-\frac{k_j t}{\eta_j}\right) \quad (5-1)$$

It is known that the viscosity η_j is temperature dependent. If the temperature is significantly lower than the glass transition temperature, $T \ll T_g$, then the viscosity can be expressed via an Arrhenius relationship as

$$\eta = A_H T \cdot e^{Q_H/RT} \quad (5-2)$$

with

$$Q_H = H_d + H_m \quad (5-3)$$

where H_d is the enthalpy of formation of broken bonds and H_m is the enthalpy of their motion. When the temperature is less than the glass transition temperature, $T < T_g$, the activation energy of viscosity is high because the amorphous materials are in the glassy state and most of their joining bonds are intact.

If the temperature is significantly higher than the glass transition temperature, $T \gg T_g$, then the viscosity can be expressed as

$$\eta = A_H T \cdot e^{Q_L/RT} \quad (5-4)$$

with

$$Q_L = H_m \quad (5-5)$$

When the temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature, $T > T_g$, the activation energy of viscosity is low because amorphous materials are melted and have most of their joining bonds broken, which facilitates flow.

If the temperature is increased, the viscosity will decrease, which is equivalent to increase test time in our damage model. Then the viscosity at different temperature can be described by b_T as

$$b_T = b_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\eta}{\eta'} \quad (5-6)$$

Where η' is the viscosity at the reference temperature T_0 . b_T can be got from (5-2) or (5-4) as

$$b_T = \frac{\eta}{\eta'} = \frac{T}{T_0} e^{\frac{Q}{R}(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0})} \quad (5-7)$$

where Q takes the value Q_H or Q_L according to the temperature. Then

$$\log b_T = \frac{Q}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \log \frac{T}{T_0} \quad (5-8)$$

In Miyano's work [18], time and temperature can be transformed simply by time-temperature shift factor a_T from the creep compliance of the resin without any further interpretation.

$$\log a_T = \frac{Q}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (5-9)$$

By comparing the time-temperature shift factor a_T [18] with (5-8), we can see the values of a_T and b_T are very approximate. By contrast, in the present damage model the temperature will affect test time through the effect upon viscosity, which is a further interpretation of TTSP applied to a stress relaxation test.

6. APPLICATION

A displayed equation is numbered flush right, using Arabic numbers in parentheses. It should be centered, leaving a 6pt space above and below to separate it from the surrounding text.

6.1 Determination of the parameters in the Wiechert model

Measurements were undertaken of the time and temperature dependence of the relaxation modulus and tensile strength in the transverse direction of the UD composite formulated by T700 carbon fibre and VTM 264-1 resin produced by Cytec Industries Inc. The fraction of the fibre and resin are 65% and 35% respectively. The curing condition is 80°C for 5 h, 120°C for 1 h. The specimen design for the stress relaxation tests is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Stress relaxation test specimen drawing.

In order to obtain the relaxation modulus, tensile stress relaxation tests were carried out from 50°C to 120°C in steps of 10°C. The results are summarized in Figure 3 which depicts the master curve for the relaxation modulus when the reference temperature is 50 °C. This master curve is plotted by taking the shift factor determined by (5-8). The activation energy is 298.4 kJ/mol which is determined from the shift factor between 80°C and 90°C.

After obtaining the relaxation curve at reference temperature (50°C), the Wiechert model parameters can be extracted from Figure 3 by using constrained least squares (MATLAB function lsqnonneg) so that none of the stiffnesses or viscosities in the Wichert model are negative. The resulting parameters are shown in Table 1 and the resulting relaxation modulus is plotted in Figure 4.

Table 1: values of k_j and η_j

	k_j (MPa)	η_j (Mpa·s)
1	166.156372215027	0.166156372215027
2	134.452070022020	1.34452070022020
3	0	0
4	127.587859897565	127.587859897565
5	60.3305917040517	603.305917040517
6	270.044438188991	27004.4438188991
7	125.214793535284	125214.793535284
8	278.800556308537	2788005.56308537
9	140.815264973125	14081526.4973125
10	725.029263649235	725029263.649235
11	586.336987964343	5863369879.64343
12	1116.92757728148	111692757728.148
13	1687.63105288540	1687631052885.40
14	1190.21723279161	11902172327916.1
15	921.530245349519	92153024534951.9

Figure 3: Master curve of relaxation modulus at the reference temperature (50°C)

Figure 4: Relaxation modulus at the reference temperature (50°C) described by the Wiechert model

6.2 Determination of the parameters of the damage evolution

The damage evolution in the transverse direction of the UD composites is represented by (4-8). The damage parameters h and λ can be determined from the stress-strain curve at any temperature obeying Arrhenius equation. A constant strain rate test was designed at 0.1mm/min for UD composite at 90° at 90°C in order to measure the stress-strain curve shown in Figure 5. Then the damage parameters h and λ can be obtained from this curve by comparing the prediction without damage evolution. The parameters h and λ are obtained by least squares as 2.7381 and 0.0117 respectively.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curve of UD composite at 90° comparing with prediction without damage evolution

6.3 Stress-strain curves prediction and comparison

After obtaining the pure viscoelastic properties described by the parameters in the Wiechert model in Table 1, the damage evolution information described by the parameters h and λ in the Weibull distribution and the activation energy Q , the stress-strain curve may be predicted for any loading rate and any temperature using equations (4-8) and (5-8). Figure 6 to Figure 9 show the stress-strain curves comparing the model predictions with the experimental data.

Figure 6: stress-strain curve with damage evolution comparison of 90° UD composites at 50°C.

Figure 7: stress-strain curve with damage evolution comparison of 90° UD composites at 70°C at.

Figure 8: stress-strain curve with damage evolution comparison of 90° UD composites at 90°C.

Figure 9: stress-strain curve with damage evolution comparison of 90° UD composites at 110°C.

It can be seen from Figure 6 to Figure 8 that the predicted stress-strain curves fit the experimental data very well. This proves that our damage model works well when predicting the damage evolution of transverse direction of the UD composites. But this damage model still cannot predict the failure of the specimens since the specimen usually fails before the maximum stress predicted by (4-9). If the failure is determined by (4-9), the strength of transverse UD composite can be predict at varies loading rate at 50°C as

Figure 10: Strength of transverse UD composites at varies loading rate at reference temperature.

When the temperature is approaching to 110°C, the prediction cannot fit the experimental data. This means that the Arrhenius equation does not work well for VTM 264_1 (Figure 3) higher than 110°C which is near the glass transition temperature (120°C). Meanwhile, the damage evolution law is affected by the low viscosity as well.

7. CONCLUSION

A CDM based damage representation based on S Li's work has been presented to model the effects of a specific and fixed level of damage on the linear viscoelastic UD composites. A damage evolution law relating to a viscoelastic material in one dimension was then obtained by assuming defects in a RVE can be developed into a crack by a corresponding strain. A complete damage model for linear viscoelastic UD composites with a specific matrix cracks was formulated. The TTSP approach is interpreted by the temperature effect on the viscosity without the need for calculation of "reduced time" which lacks rigour and can lead to confusion. Finally, the whole process of using this damage model to predict the properties of the UD composite during deformation is described in this paper and the result is compared with experimental data. The stress-strain curve predictions fit the experimental data perfectly in a certain range. However, this model still cannot predict the failure or the strength precisely.

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